

AREA MARKETING IS A TOOL TO MOVE LOCATIONS TO
CUSTOMERS

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Abstract. *In article on the basis of research of dual aspect of "place" as marketing-mix component the concept, essence, kinds, methods and principles of marketing of territories which to serve as the important tool of promoting of places to the clients reveals.*

Keywords. Customers, modernization, economy, competitiveness, development, market, factors.

In the conditions of modernization of the economy of Uzbekistan, competitiveness of regions is an important factor of sustainable development of regions. The penetration of the regions of our country into the world markets requires increasing the competitiveness of the regions. In order to achieve this, it is necessary to support and develop the "marketing concept based on regions" in our country, which helps to create a positive image of the regions and raise their international reputation. Because the main goal of regional marketing is to strengthen the position and fame of the region in international competition. Because, in the conditions of market economy, regions gain a new essence: regions turn from a geographic, spatial unit into a unique product (goods) with value and consumer value.

Words such as Swiss watches, French perfumes, Venetian bottles, Vologda lace, Belgian chocolates, Egyptian pyramids, Samarkand bread, Khorezm lazgi, Karshi tandirkabob, Bukhara monuments have the feature of introducing them to a wide community, customers and investors as famous brands of these regions.

Marketing experts consider such famous phrases to be examples of successful territory marketing.

In Uzbekistan, the idea, principles and methods of marketing are actively supported in the process of selling goods and services. Many scientific works have been written and practical works have been carried out in our country on the marketing of goods and services. Regional marketing is still an unexplored field. In the process of moving certain places, the concept of marketing is almost not used in our country.

The "place" element of marketing in the service sector, according to T.A. Sebekina, has a double meaning: firstly, it is the place of service provision, which depends on the point of contact with customers or the location of the enterprise, and secondly, it is the marketing channels for the realization of services.

V.P. Radchenko divides the marketing object of rural areas into two types of structure: on the one hand, it is a regional product in the form of material goods and services created in the rural area, and on the other hand, socio-cultural factors (image, brand of the area, its socio-cultural and the region itself as a set of ethnic characteristics) serves as a target for stakeholders and external entities in choosing the directions of implementation of consumer efforts of the region. He recommends including the following four elements in the marketing mix of rural areas: "people", "place", "processes", "product".

According to F. Kotler: "Places, like goods and services, need accurate and skillful marketing. Each city or commune needs to identify its unique characteristics and effectively disseminate information about its competitive advantages to current and future customers it seeks to support. This is not a simple task.

According to G. Golubkova, "Place marketing" is defined as an activity aimed at creating, supporting or changing the efforts or relationships of customers applied to particular places. In other words, place marketing is an activity aimed at changing and creating attitudes and efforts of stakeholders towards specific places.

It would be appropriate to distinguish between the terms "territory (place) marketing" and "territorial marketing". In our opinion, if the first is aimed at selling and moving individual places, the second is related to activities aimed at accelerating the sale of goods and services created by enterprises within the region. As a result of such thinking, there is an opportunity to justify the concept of marketing based on territories (places).

Philip Kotler, a well-known marketing scientist, developed the basics of place marketing and divided it into four types. These are economic activity marketing of zones, recreation marketing, accommodation marketing and real estate investment marketing (Figure 1).

[Source: the image was compiled by the author based on the book "Marketing Fundamentals" by F. Kotler].

1. Fig. Types of Place Marketing

O.A. Kozlova includes the following in the basic principles of regional marketing: 1. To implement various projects move the area as a place; 2.

Effectively solving the problems of the economy at different levels; 3. Long-term sustainable development; 4. Influencing the behavior of subjects in the investment market and the process of forming consumers.

In foreign literature on place marketing, the following levels of non-commercial area marketing are distinguished: planning the most appropriate combination of regional goods and services; create incentives for users of these products/services; improving the use of regional products/services; moving the image and value of places that are able to guarantee that potential users are aware of their benefits.

In order for the region to move itself towards the target customers, several important strategic decisions must be made. Four broad strategies are distinguished to attract visitors, develop business and increase the region's exports (Figure 2):

First, image marketing. The image of the region is currently becoming an important economic resource and a factor of competitiveness of the country, region, and cities. One of the goals of image marketing is successful, honest and reliable advertising is to create a slogan.

2. Fig. Methods used in the process of area marketing

For example, experts successfully use the advertising slogan "Bukhara - a museum in the open air" when promoting Bukhara's tourist opportunities. In

forming a positive image of the region, it is important to organize fairs, various festivals, various theatrical performances such as "Sound of Centuries", publishing various information and advertising publications, and creating souvenir products. Craftsmanship traditions, creative teams, national cuisine, customs are the basis of the image of the region. and pictures can stand.

Second, attraction marketing. This area marketing strategy is aimed at increasing the attractiveness of the area for residence, business placement, and tourist visits. It is necessary to study the features unique to each region and use them to increase the competitiveness of the region and benefit from it. It is possible to ensure the attractiveness of areas for people by developing architecture, turning the old part of the city into a tourist and shopping area for walking, repairing monuments and performing landscaping works in the area. For example, as a result of comprehensive renovation and beautification works carried out under the leadership of our President in Bahauddin Naqshband Memorial Complex, the attractiveness of the shrine of the Seventh Pir has increased.

Third, infrastructure marketing. Raising the image of the places and increasing their attractiveness requires the development of the infrastructure of the regions. Infrastructure marketing includes issues such as the condition of roads, personal safety, compliance with community rules, transportation, communication, water supply, cleanliness of the area, availability of parks, stability of the financial and banking system, and tax benefits.

Fourth, people marketing. This strategy involves advertising to the population living within the area. People marketing can be implemented in the following forms: use of well-known persons of the place in advertising the area in the market; promote the figures and initiatives of local leaders; demonstrate the availability of qualified personnel in the area; to represent the activities of people with entrepreneurial skills in the region; advertising the success of people who have moved from other places in the area.

Thus, in the conditions of the market economy, we think that the economy

of Uzbekistan will achieve more rapid development due to the effective use of regional marketing ideas in our country by researching the image of regions as a unique product (commodity) with value and consumer value.

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